

COMPETITIVENESS OF UZBEKISTAN’S AGRI-FOOD EXPORTS

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Abstract. *The article analyzes the export performance of Uzbekistan’s fruit and vegetable products and evaluates their competitiveness in the global market using practical index-based methods. The analysis is based on data from the International Trade Centre, and 12 products classified under the HS-4 code were selected for the study. The Trade Balance Index was used to determine whether the country is a net exporter or importer of these products. Competitiveness in exports was assessed using the Balassa and Vollrath indices. The analysis revealed that 9 out of the 12 products are competitive, and Uzbekistan acts as a net exporter of these goods. The findings highlight the need for the country to diversify its export basket and expand into new international markets.*

Keywords: *Uzbekistan, agri-food exports, trade balance index, revealed comparative advantage, relative trade advantage.*

1. Introduction

The development of agriculture is essential for ensuring food security in any country. Agricultural advancement not only meets domestic food demand but also contributes to employment generation, serves as a source of raw materials for industry, and creates a foundation for agricultural exports. In the global trade system, the export of agricultural products-particularly fruits and vegetables-plays a crucial role in the economic development of countries (Santeramo et al., 2024). This sector is characterized by intense competition, and a country's stable position in international markets largely depends on product competitiveness, export diversification, and market expansion. Competitiveness is a fundamental element of market economies (Mizik, 2021). Among Central Asian countries, Uzbekistan has emerged as one of the most dynamic exporters of agricultural products. In recent years, the country has not only increased the volume of fruit and vegetable exports but has also actively pursued access to new markets. However, limitations in the export structure and uneven levels of product competitiveness remain key challenges in this process.

In this context, analyzing Uzbekistan’s position in the foreign trade of fruit and vegetable products and assessing their competitiveness carries significant importance from the perspective of economic policy. The primary objective of this study is to identify the country’s export potential, competitive advantages, and position in the international market in relation to these products. For this purpose, data from the International Trade Centre (ITC) were used to select 12 key fruit and vegetable products classified under the HS-4 code. Their export performance was evaluated using various trade indices, including the Balassa and Vollrath indices. The findings of this study aim to shed light on Uzbekistan’s potential in this sector and to outline strategic directions for future development.

2. Methodology

The primary data for this study were obtained from the International Trade Centre (ITC) for the period between 2017 and 2024. During these years, data on fruit and vegetable products classified under the Harmonized System (HS) at the 4-digit level were collected. The selected HS-4 codes for the study include: 0702 (Tomatoes, fresh or chilled), 0703 (Onions, shallots, garlic, leeks, and other alliaceous vegetables, fresh or chilled), 0704 (Cabbages, cauliflowers, kohlrabi, kale, and similar edible brassicas, fresh or chilled), 0705 (Lettuce *lactuca sativa* and chicory *Cichorium* spp., fresh or chilled), 0706 (Carrots, turnips, salad beetroot, salsify, celeriac, radishes, and similar edible roots, fresh), 0707 (Cucumbers and gherkins, fresh or chilled), 0805 (Citrus fruits, fresh or dried), 0806 (Grapes, fresh or dried), 0807 (Melons, including watermelons, and papayas, fresh), 0808 (Apples, pears, and quinces, fresh), 0809 (Apricots, cherries, peaches including nectarines, plums, and sloes, fresh), 0810 (Strawberries, raspberries, blackberries, currants, gooseberries, and other fresh berries).

To evaluate the competitiveness of these products in the global market, one of the widely used methods is the Revealed Comparative Advantage (RCA) index. The Balassa index, introduced by Balassa (1965), remains one of the most significant tools for empirical analysis of international trade specialization (Liu & Gao, 2019). In this study, the RCA index was used to analyze the comparative advantage of Uzbekistan's fruit and vegetable exports in global markets. The index is calculated as the ratio between a product's share in the country's total exports and its share in total world exports (Bashimov, 2024), as shown below:

$$RCA = \frac{\frac{X_{ij}}{X_j}}{\frac{X_{jw}}{X_w}} \quad (1)$$

Where:

X_{ij} : Exports of product j by country i ,

X_j : Total exports by country i ,

X_{jw} : Global exports of product j ,

X_w : Total world exports.

If $RCA > 1$, the country is considered to have a comparative advantage and export competitiveness in product j . If $RCA < 1$, it is considered not to have a comparative advantage.

Following Balassa's work, several alternative indices were developed, among them the indices proposed by Vollrath, which address some of the limitations of Balassa's approach. While the Balassa index uses only export data and includes double counting of the same product in the numerator and denominator, the Vollrath indices incorporate both export and import data, offering a more comprehensive view of trade competitiveness. One of the key indicators in Vollrath's methodology is the Relative Export Advantage (RXA) index (Taghiyev & Aliguliyeva, 2025), defined as:

$$RXA = \frac{\frac{X_{ij}}{X_{uj}}}{\frac{X_{ir}}{X_{ur}}} \quad (2)$$

$$RMA = \frac{\frac{M_{ij}}{M_{ir}}}{\frac{M_{uj}}{M_{ur}}} \quad (3)$$

$$RTA_{ij} = RXA_{ij} - RMA_{ij} \quad (4)$$

Where:

X_{ij} , M_{ij} : Exports and imports of product j by country i ,

X_{nj} , M_{nj} : Total exports and imports of product j by the reference group,

X_{ir} , M_{ir} : Total exports and imports by country i ,

X_{nr} , M_{nr} : Total exports and imports by the reference group.

The Balassa and Vollrath indices often produce similar results. In Vollrath’s framework, a positive RTA value indicates that the country has a competitive advantage, while a negative value suggests a lack of competitiveness in that product (Fertő & Hubbard, 2003). Another index used in this study is the Trade Balance Index (TBI), developed by Lafay (1992). This index measures whether a country is a net exporter or a net importer of a particular product (Purwono et al., 2022):

$$TBI_{ij} = (X_{ij} - M_{ij}) / (X_{ij} + M_{ij}) \quad (5)$$

Where:

X_{ij} : Exports of product j by country i ,

M_{ij} : Imports of product j by country i .

The TBI yields values between -1 and $+1$. A positive value indicates that the country is a net exporter, while a negative value implies a net importer of that product.

3. Results and analysis

Uzbekistan is one of the leading exporters of agricultural products. In 2024, the country’s fruit and vegetable exports reached nearly 2 billion USD (ITC). Between 2020 and 2024, vegetable exports increased significantly. The development of agriculture, which accounts for 18.3% of the country’s GDP (World Bank, 2024), is also contributing to the expansion of export opportunities. The growing diversity of exported products is transforming the country into a key exporter for those commodities. Based on calculations using the trade balance index, it has been determined that Uzbekistan was a net exporter in 10 out of 12 selected products during the period 2017–2024. Tables 1 and 2 present the RCA and RTA results for the selected 12 products.

Table 1. RCA results

Year/HS -4 code	070 2	0703	0704	070 5	0706	070 7	080 5	080 6	080 7	080 8	080 9	081 0
2017	7.76	2.45	4.72	1.88	6.37	3.1	0.7	28.6	1.6	1	38.7	5.9
2018	8.69	5.41	8.41	1.94	12.1 1	4.9	0.4	31.4	2.9	1.2	69.7	4.6
2019	9.56	12.5 1	12.9 1	0.61	22.0 3	6.2	1.2	28.1	4.3	3.5	37.7	4.7
2020	8.61	6.69	7.73	0.5	8.8	3	0.7	22.7	12.1	1.3	34.1	4.5
2021	8.61	6.4	8.48	0.5	11.1	5.2	0.5	28.8	8.4	0.7	27.5	3.3
2022	8.72	10.0 4	16.4 4	0.9	18.1	3.3	0.6	39.3	13.7	1.7	24.8	5.2
2023	4.93	8.5	8.24	0.8	7.5	2.2	0.3	16.3	10.8	1.2	27.9	2
2024	4.02	10.1	18.5	0.9	14.7	1.8	0.3	18.3	6.2	1.2	19.1	1.7

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Source: Calculated by the author.

Table 2. RTA results

	0702	0703	0704	0705	0706	0707	0805	0806	0807	0808	0809	0810
2017	7.8	2.4	4.7	1.9	6.4	3.2	-0.03	29.5	1.6	0.8	40.1	5.9
2018	8.8	5.4	8.5	1.9	12.2	5	-0.13	32.5	2.9	1.1	74.2	4.6
2019	9.7	12.7	13.1	0.6	22.5	6.2	0.4	29.1	4.3	3.3	39.3	4.7
2020	8.7	6.4	7.8	0.5	8.9	3	0.3	23.4	12.2	1	35.5	4.5
2021	8.7	6.4	8.5	0.5	11.1	5.2	-0.3	29.8	8.4	0.07	28.3	3.2
2022	8.8	9.9	16.6	0.9	18.4	3.3	-0.7	40.9	13.8	0.4	25.4	5.1
2023	5	8.4	8.3	0.8	7.4	2.2	-0.9	16.5	11	-0.1	28.9	1.9
2024	-0.1	10	19.1	0.9	15	1.8	-2.1	18.6	6.3	-1.4	19.7	1.5

Source: Calculated by the author.

Conclusion

The study focuses on the top 12 most exported fruit and vegetable products from Uzbekistan during the period 2017-2024, analyzed using empirical methods. The research reveals that, according to the TBI index, 10 products are export-oriented, while 9 products demonstrate a comparative advantage based on the RTA and RCA indices. The highest RCA values are observed in nectarines, plums, and grapes, whereas citrus fruits exhibit the lowest values.

Statistical data on Uzbekistan’s fruit and vegetable exports indicate that the export commodities are concentrated in a few countries in terms of value. This concentration affects the stability of export revenues, increases political risks, and strengthens the country’s dependency on a limited number of markets. Therefore, there is a need to diversify the range of export destinations and reduce the concentration of export markets.

REFERENCES

- Balassa, B. (1965), Trade liberalisation and “revealed” comparative advantage. *The Manchester School*, 33 (2), 99-123.
- Bashimov, G. (2024). TARIM VE GIDA ÜRÜNLERİNİN REKABET ÜSTÜNLÜĞÜNÜN AKÜ İNDEKSİ İLE ÖLÇÜLMESİ: ÖZBEKİSTAN ÖRNEĞİ. *Dünya Multidisipliner Araştırmalar Dergisi*, 7(1), 45-61.
- <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/NV.AGR.TOTL.ZS?locations=UZ>
- Fertő, I., & Hubbard, L. J. (2003). Revealed comparative advantage and competitiveness in Hungarian agri–food sectors. *World Economy*, 26(2), 247-259.
- Lafay, Gerard. 1992. The measurement of revealed comparative advantages. In *International Trade Modelling*. Berlin: Springer, pp. 209–34
- Liu, B., & Gao, J. (2019). Understanding the non-Gaussian distribution of revealed comparative advantage index and its alternatives. *International Economics*, 158, 1-11.
- Mizik, T. (2021). Agri-food trade competitiveness: A review of the literature. *Sustainability*, 13(20), 11235.
- Purwono, R., Sugiharti, L., Handoyo, R. D., & Esquivias, M. A. (2022). Trade liberalization and comparative advantage: Evidence from Indonesia and Asian trade partners. *Economies*, 10(4), 80.

9. Santeramo, F. G., Jelliffe, J., & Hoekman, B. (2024). Agri-food value chains and the global food dollar: The role of trade and services. *Food Policy*, 127, 102706.
10. Taghiyev, J. (2025). Competitiveness Analysis of Uzbekistan's Grape Export (2017-2023). *Available at SSRN 5370719*.
11. Taghiyev, J., & Aliguliyeva, K. (2025). ORTA ASYA TÜRK DEVLETLERİNİN ELEKTRİK İHRACATININ KARŞILAŞTIRMALI ÜSTÜNLÜĞÜ VE REKABET GÜCÜ ANALİZİ (COMPARATIVE ADVANTAGE AND COMPETITIVENESS ANALYSIS OF ELECTRICITY EXPORTS OF CENTRAL ASIAN TURKIC STATES). *Available at SSRN 5388561*.
12. Tağıyev, C. (2024). Yaşıl enerjinin Azərbaycanın enerji istehsalında artan rolu: Elektrik enerjisi ixracı və rəqabətqabiliyyətlilik təhlili. *ISCEMR*
13. Taghiyev, J. (2025). Analysis of the competitiveness of persimmon export in Azerbaijan. *Scientific Collection «InterConf*, 54(236), 61-69.
14. Trademap.https://www.trademap.org/Country_SelProductCountry_TS.aspx?nvm=1%7c860%7c%7c%7c%7c08%7c%7c%7c2%7c1%7c1%7c2%7c2%7c1%7c2%7c1%7c1%7c1